

ON SOME BIOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF NATURAL COUMARINS*

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Natural coumarins occupy an important place among plant constituents. Coumarin (I), the simplest member of the series, was isolated from tonka bean (*Dipteryx odorata* Willd.) by Vogel¹ in 1820 and immediately attracted the attention of perfumers on account of its pleasant and persistent odour. Coumarin has since been located in more than 80 different plants. Dihydrocoumarin (II) has a similar odour and some methoxy- and hydroxy-coumarins have also this characteristic, though not pronounced. More complex coumarins are practically odourless at the ordinary temperature. A systematic correlation between aroma and chemical constitution in the coumarin series is lacking, though the odour seems to be associated with the lactonic structure and presence of a 3:4-double bond.

Coumarin (I)

Dihydrocoumarin (II)

Daphnetin (III)

Many natural coumarins affect the living cells of plants and animals in various ways. The influence of coumarins in bringing about biochemical changes is being gradually recognized in many fields of study. Most of the work has been done with the parent member of the group, namely coumarin, and many interesting results have been recorded.

Coumarin itself, which is a fairly common plant metabolite, inhibits the germination and subsequent root-growth of plants. Klebs² observed its toxic action on algae, while Shreiner, Reed and Skinner³ recorded its inhibitory effects on the growth of wheat. Cameron⁴ reported that daphnetin (III), another member of this group, behaved in the same way. Sigmund⁵ noted the effects of both daphnetin and its isomer, æsculetin, on seed germination. It has since been shown that a number of unsaturated lactones including coumarin possess what is called the "blastocoline" effect, *i.e.*, the property to suppress the germination of seeds⁶, at low concentrations.

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The phytocidal action of coumarin was also studied by Audus and Quastel⁷, who observed that coumarin exerted a marked inhibition of both germination and root-growth, the latter being more susceptible than germination. Further, its action is a differential one, carrot, for example, being 20 times as sensitive as cress. The formative effects on the hypocotyl are also marked. The inhibitory effects of coumarin, being reversible, are supposed to arise from loose combinations or easily dissociated compounds of coumarin with enzymes or metabolites of the plant cell. It is now believed that enzymes are inactivated by addition of the sulphhydryl groups to the 3:4 double-bond of coumarin. Thiourea lifts this inhibition.

Coumarin also reduces the germination of the eyes of potato tubers⁸, but the rate of germination of barley grains is increased by their immersion in coumarin solution (10^{-7} to $10^{-10}M$) for 24 hours. It has thus an activity like that of indole-3-acetic acid. The root-growth of tomato is inhibited by a concentration of 0.05 mg./100 c.c., but is stimulated at a higher dilution⁹ of 0.0001-0.0005 mg./100 c.c.—an interesting observation.

The inhibiting activity of a number of coumarins is shown in Table I (F. Moewus, *Naturforsch. u. Med. in Deutschland*, 1939-46, Band 40, Biochem. Teil II, p. 185).

- There is also a good probability that coumarins act as growth regulators in a number of plants. This is supported by the fact that the plant, *Melilotus officinalis*, in which coumarin normally occurs, is not capable of thriving when made coumarin-free by proper breeding¹⁰.

Tobacco plants infected with tomato wilt virus, and virus-infected tubers and oat roots have been found to contain scopoletin (IV).

Scopoletin (IV)

Umbelliferone (V)

Roots having the highest concentration of scopoletin showed the slowest growth¹¹. Both umbelliferone (V) and scopoletin are produced in the sound (uninjured) part of the injured sweet potato. These inhibit the growth of *Ceratostomella fimbriata*, a fungus, in dilutions of 1:1000 and 1:4000 respectively. Appearance, under ultraviolet light, of blue fluorescence can be used to distinguish healthy from injured sweet potato affected by this fungus and many other pathogens¹².

The blastocholine action of coumarins is not confined to plants. Grimm¹³ observed that tadpoles of *Xenopus levis* brought into solutions of coumarin (1:10⁸ to 1:4 × 10⁹) for 10-20 days after hatching developed into frogs inferior in weight as

compared to controls. Further, coumarin (1 in 2500) and æsculetin (1 in 5000) could arrest or retard the growth of *Rana esculenta* at the larval stage. It would be quite interesting to see how the youngs of other animals behave towards these and allied substances.

TABLE I
Inhibiting effect of different coumarins.

<i>Coumarin.</i>	<i>Conc.</i>	<i>% Germination.</i>	<i>% Inhibition.</i>
Ayapin	1 : 10 ⁶	87	19
Bergapten	1 : 10 ⁶	83	15
Pimpinellin	1 : 10 ⁶	73	23
Seselin	1 : 10 ⁶	59	30
Daphnetin	1 : 2.10 ⁶	80	29
Xanthotoxin	1 : 5.10 ⁶	77	59
Xanthotoxin	1 : 5.10 ⁶	83	34
Nodakenin (glucoside)	1 : 2.10 ⁴	93	9
Nodakenin (glucoside)	1 : 10 ⁵	89	0
Nodakenetin	1 : 2.10 ⁴	83	35
Nodakenetin	1 : 10 ⁵	87	12
Skimmin (glucoside)	1 : 2.10 ⁴	93	30
Skimmin (glucoside)	1 : 10 ⁵	92	5
Umbelliferone (aglycone)	1 : 2.10 ⁴	97	60
Umbelliferone (aglycone)	1 : 4.10 ⁴	88	50
Umbelliferone (aglycone)	1 : 8.10 ⁴	91	37
Umbelliferone (aglycone)	1 : 10 ⁵	88	19
Cichoriin (glycoside)	1 : 2.10 ⁴	93	+5
Æsculetin (aglycone)	1 : 2.10 ⁴	91	+3

Coumarin has interesting cytogenetic properties. A technique of chromosome analysis with the help of coumarin has been developed by Sharma and Bal¹⁴ and good results have been obtained. Pre-treatment in coumarin for short periods results in satisfactory clarification of plant chromosomes, but prolonged treatment causes fragmentation, and chromosomes become pycnotic. Cytological and macroscopical effects of coumarin and its derivatives have been studied by Quercioli¹⁵ in *Allium cepa*. Pre-prophasic inhibition, stickiness, mutagenic action, C-mitotic effects etc. are produced with mutagenic concentrations of these chemicals. It has been suggested that coumarins attack mainly interkinetic chromosomes while the mutagenic action of other compounds concerns the mitotic chromosomes. The substances studied include the acetyl derivatives of umbelliferone and æsculetin, which also exhibit root-inducing effect.

Coumarins behave differently towards animals. de Moura Campos¹⁶ noticed a true curare-like action of coumarin, while Marolda¹⁷ observed a diminution of tone and decrease or suppression of peristalsis on subjecting isolated strips of rabbit's small intestine to increasing concentrations of coumarin.

Coumarin acts as a narcotic for some animals (*e.g.* rabbit, earthworm) and as a sedative and hypnotic for mice. Some larger animals, such as sheep, dogs and horses, can be killed by coumarin, the lethal doses being 5 g., 0.6-0.8 g. and 40 g. respectively¹⁸. Moderate quantities have no marked effect on human subjects except its curare-like action. Fraxin (VI) causes paralysis of the central nervous system of frogs and mice on intravenous injection¹⁹.

Fraxin (VI)

[Æsculin : R = C₆H₁₁O₅ (VII)
Æsculetin : R = H]

Both urine volume and uric acid elimination in rabbits are increased by administration of fraxin. Fraxin caused increase in urine volume to 1.6 times per hour on an average for 8 hours. During this period, the uric acid in urine increased to 2.1 times the normal. It has therefore been found to be superior to "atophan" in the treatment of gout²⁰.

Some simpler coumarin derivatives have pronounced activity like that of vitamin P. The capillary resistance of normal guinea-pigs is raised and the capillary fragility of scorbutic guinea-pigs is decreased by injections of æsculin (VII). Ingestion of 20 mg. of the substance by human subjects increases capillary resistance and the effect persists for more than a week²¹.

Dicoumarol (VIII)

Herniarin (IX)

Considerable advantage has been gained by the discovery of "dicoumarol" (VIII), the haemorrhagic principle of "spoiled sweet clover" (improperly cured hay) which delays coagulation of blood²². Structurally dicoumarol is different from other natural coumarins in the sense that it has two coumarin nuclei bridged by a methylene group. It is the causative factor of what is known as the "sweet clover disease" in cattle. Dicoumarol is employed in medicine in the treatment of thrombosis and allied conditions and to control the bad effects of vitamin K₁. This anticoagulant probably acts by hindering the formation of prothrombin²³. All coumarins having anti-vitamin K activity are metabolised in the body to salicylic acid which has a short-

term action similar to that of dicoumarol²⁴. The liver is the site of dicoumarol activity and this fact has been established by using a specimen having labelled carbon in the methylene group. But since it damages the liver, and its action is slow, search for synthetic compounds was stimulated. So far, the synthetic coumarin derivatives, known in trade as Tromexan, Cumopyran and Marcoumar, have been found to be much better remedies, which are active in small doses and free from the disadvantages of dicoumarol²⁵.

Dicoumarol is an effective rodenticide²⁶. It is also a strong blastocholine for wheat and cress test plants. It inhibits growth and cell division in chicken fibroblast cultures²⁷. In glaucoma, dicoumarol exerts an anticoagulant action on sclerotic and obliterative processes, thereby improving circulation in the eye and producing an enlargement of the visual field²⁸.

While dicoumarol is an anticoagulant, it is interesting to note that some simpler coumarins have the opposite effect. Herniarin (IX) and ayapin (X) have been found to possess a remarkable haemostatic property and are active both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. They are well tolerated by, and are non-toxic to, rabbits. Scopoletin, æsculetin dimethyl ether and daphnetin dimethyl ether also possess this property though the intensity of action is much less. The corresponding phenolic compounds are inactive. The mechanism of blood coagulation caused by these products is not known²⁹.

Ayapin (X)

Psoralene (XI)

It is now generally recognized that the unsaturated lactonic structure is of frequent occurrence in pharmacologically important natural substances and is also encountered in some plant materials with bacteriostatic activity. Coumarin was found to have a low bacteriostatic activity, while dicoumarol inhibited the growth of *Bacillus anthracis*³⁰ in a dilution of 1:500,000.

The action of natural coumarins on fungi and other micro-organisms does not seem to have received much attention. Chakraborty *et al.*³¹ studied the action of 15 natural coumarins against *Curvularia lunata* and *Aspergillus niger*. The highest activity was shown by psoralene (XI), seselin (XII), luvangetin (XIII) and xanthyletin (XIV) against *C. lunata* while seselin was only moderately active against *A. niger*.

Seseleg. (XII)

Luvangetin (XIII)

Xanthyletin (XIV)

Pimpinellin (XV)

isoPimpinellin (XVI)

Dicoumarol has a decidedly antibacterial action. At a dilution of 1:50,000 it stopped the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. albus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. It also inhibited the growth of *Pasteurella avicida* in a dilution of 1:25,000, but *Streptococcus faecalis* and some other organisms were not affected²².

Novobiocin²³, a new antibiotic isolated from a *Streptomyces* sp., has been proved to be a coumarin derivative having the structure (XVI)²⁴. The bacterial strains inhibited by this antibiotic include *Micrococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Diplococcus*, *Neisseria*, *Corynebacterium*, *Pasteurella*, *Erysipelothrix* and *Proteus*²⁵. Staphylococci are the most sensitive among the Gram-positive cocci. The antibacterial spectrum of this antibiotic corresponds generally with those of penicillin and erythromycin. But *in vitro* it is less potent than penicillin or erythromycin. It is equally effective by oral and subcutaneous route and is highly effective against Staphylococci resistant to other antibiotics.

Novobiocin (XVI)

The growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* was also inhibited by mesul in a dilution of 3:10⁶. This substance is a coumarin derivative obtained from *Mesua ferrea* but its complete structure has not yet been determined. The substance is feebly active when compared with penicillin but almost as active as allicin, the antibiotic principle of garlic. It had no effect on the fungi, *A. niger*, *C. lunata*, *Alternaria solani* and *Helminthosporium sativum*²⁶.

Calophyllolide, a complex coumarin isolated from *Calophyllum inophyllum*, showed tuberculostatic activity against a strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in a dilution of 1:20,000. The activity was lowered in presence of serum²⁷. Tuberculostatic activity²⁸ is also exhibited by pimpinellin (XV) and isopimpinellin (XVI) in

dilutions of $1:1-2 \times 10^6$. *Æsculin* can be used for the identification of bacteria, for it can be hydrolysed by some bacteria (*e.g.*, lactic acid bacteria, most streptococci and enterococci) producing *æsculetin*³⁹.

Coumarin and some of its derivatives having m.p.'s lower than $70-100^\circ$ have been generally found to have strong anthelmintic action⁴⁰, while many natural coumarins, particularly those with a furan ring-system, are toxic to fish. Employing *Lebistes reticulatus* as test animals, Späth and Kuffner⁴¹ observed the lethal effect of the following coumarins at the concentrations noted against them in 8 hours (Table II). In the early stage, the compounds exert a stimulant action, but soon the fish floats on its back, gradually stops moving and ultimately dies. Angelicin (XXIV), however, induces narcosis.

TABLE II

Coumarin	1:6,800	Oxypeucedanin (XIX)	1:70,000
<i>Allo-imperatorin</i> (XVII)	1:40,000	Xanthotoxin (XX)	1:70,000
<i>Pimpinellin</i> (XV)	1:50,000	<i>Imperatorin</i> (XXI)	1:74,000
<i>isoPimpinellin</i> (XVa)	1:60,000	Osthol (XXII)	1:82,000
<i>Ostruthin</i> (XVIII)	1:67,000	Bergapten (XXIII)	1:93,000

Oxypeucedanin (XIX)

Xanthotoxin (XX)

Osthol (XXII)

Bergapten (XXIII)

Angelicin (XXIV)

These results have been supplemented by Murti and Seshadri, who observed toxicity of umbelliferone and herniarin when tested against the fresh-water fish *Haplochitus panchax*⁴².

Recently coumarins have figured prominently in the treatment of leucoderma. Oral and local administrations of psoralene-angelicin mixture obtained from *Psoralea corylifolia* have been reported to give beneficial results. *Ammi majus*, an Egyptian drug of value in the indigenous treatment of depigmented skin, has been found to contain the photo-sensitizing agents xanthotoxin, imperatorin and bergapten. The first two are said to hasten the formation of melanin. Comparatively, the active principles of *A. majus* are better than those of *Psoralea*. Though the complete cure rate is small, substantial improvement to the extent of 66% has been noticed in clinical trials⁴³.

The mechanism of action of these coumarins in stimulating pigmentation is not known. A full appraisal of the mechanism will no doubt encourage search for an effective curative drug. The Indian fruit, bael (*Aegle marmelos*), also contains imperatorin and allied compounds with a furan ring-system, and it may be worth while to study the behaviour of these compounds towards leucoderma.

This account of some interesting biochemical properties of natural coumarins is by no means complete. But, I believe, I have said enough to emphasize the fact that they are not mere metabolic products of the living cell but possess varied and often remarkable physiological actions. It is hoped that this review, although brief, would stimulate further studies of the biochemical aspects of coumarins, both natural and synthetic †.

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